

A Roadmap for Iterative Calibration of Digital Twins via Adaptive Observers

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While iterative calibration of computational models is a fundamental aspect of digital twins, it has been largely overlooked. Instead of focusing on parameter identification for static models, the implementation of digital twins requires not only high-resolution computational models, but also the ability to assimilate patient-specific data continuously.

Here, we envisage a roadmap for adaptive observers algorithms to address this challenge. By leveraging computational models and patient-specific measurements, adaptive observers enable the estimation of unmeasurable states while continuously adapting model parameters. Integrating adaptive observers into digital twins offers a paradigm shift: transforming them from static representations into living, evolving systems that advance personalized medicine.

Digital Twins | Adaptive Observers | State and Parameter Estimation | data assimilation | Personalized Medicine | Control Theory in Medicine

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Introduction

Since their conceptualization in the early 2000s, Digital Twins (DTs) have been built on three fundamental pillars: (i) a virtual model, (ii) a physical counterpart, and (iii) dynamic updating mechanisms that synchronize the first two pillars through continuous data exchange [Grieves \(2014\)](#); [Grieves and Vickers \(2016a\)](#); [Tao and Qi \(2019\)](#). The concept of digital twins was initially implemented for physical industrial products and services [Grieves \(2023\)](#). Nowadays, the aforementioned approach is widely applied in many sectors that assist forecasts and minimize emergency behavior by modeling complex systems under a wide range of real-world conditions [Grieves and Vickers \(2016b\)](#); [Tao and Qi \(2019\)](#). For instance, NASA created virtual replicas of spacecraft for design, maintenance, and monitoring [Liu et al. \(2024\)](#). Some companies employ digital twins to enhance energy production [Nikolas Noel \(2015\)](#) or diagnose and anticipate real-world issues in their facilities [Chevron Corporation \(2023\)](#). Additionally, local and state governments are employing digital twins technology for urban planning and disaster management [Tom White \(2018\)](#); [Observatory of Public Sector Innovation \(2018\)](#).

In the medical field, Medical Digital Twins (MDTs) have been envisioned as patient-specific computational models capable of supporting diagnosis, prognosis, and

therapy design [Laubenbacher et al. \(2024b\)](#); [National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine \(2023\)](#); [Niarakis et al. \(2024\)](#). MDTs offer promising solutions for testing drug efficacy, optimizing treatment plans, and predicting disease progression [Björnsson et al. \(2019\)](#); [Laubenbacher et al. \(2024a\)](#); [Niarakis et al. \(2024\)](#). Some recent applications include modeling Tuberculosis infection [Joslyn et al. \(2022\)](#), modeling virtual patient cohorts during viral infections [Jenner et al. \(2021\)](#), creating immune system simulation platforms [Castiglione and Celada \(2015\)](#); [Castiglione and Bernaschi \(2004\)](#), developing pneumonia MDTs to support decision-making processes in intensive care units [Ribeiro et al. \(2022\)](#), developing breast cancer MDTs [Jarrett et al. \(2021\)](#), and developing MDTs for leukemia [Laubenbacher et al. \(2024a\)](#). The workflow for developing MDTs, as illustrated in Figure 1, involves utilizing disease-relevant biological data to establish a generic computational model. This model is then validated using both population and patient-specific data, resulting in a personalized model. This personalized model can then be applied to the prediction and simulation of diseases [Laubenbacher et al. \(2024a\)](#).

The boundaries that govern current MDT applications are particularly evident in their dependence on static mechanistic models. These models are typically parameterized once at the beginning of the model identification process using a predefined dataset. However, these computational models remain *static* for a fixed period of time until a new and sufficiently large dataset becomes available, at which point the model parameter identification procedure is triggered once more. Therefore, while beneficial in providing a foundational understanding of complex systems, current digital twins often fail to keep up with ever-evolving data. Digital twins require continuous model updating that evolves at the same pace as new data becomes available, in order to reflect their physical counterparts accurately.

As stated in [Wright and Davidson \(2020\)](#), the ability to dynamically update or adjust the model as new data becomes available is a crucial component that differentiates a digital twin from a conventional mathematical model. Digital twins applications need to consider data assimilation frameworks that allow for continuous updates and refinements of the mechanistic model. This means going from *static* to *adaptive* systems, which are capable of responding to real-time scenarios. In this paper, we propose that adaptive observers offer a promising approach to this data assimilation challenge.

Figure 1. Medical digital twin framework. The essential parts for the development of a digital twin, according to the National Academic of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine. A crucial part is that information flows bidirectionally between the physical and virtual counterparts. The Human-2-Digital direction allows the recalibrating of the model to make accurate predictions. The Digital-2-Human direction allows valuable information for the decision-making process of practitioners to become available

In control theory, an observer is an algorithm that provides an estimate of the state variables of a real system by combining information from system inputs, system outputs, and a model of the system's dynamics [Chen \(1984\)](#); [Kalman et al. \(1960\)](#); [Simon \(2006\)](#).

Adaptive observers, on the other hand, offer the ability to estimate unmeasured states while enabling real-time parameter recalibration [Besancon et al. \(2006\)](#). Adaptive observers differ from traditional observer designs, such as the Luenberger observer or Kalman filter, by extending the observer paradigm to joint state-parameter estimation. While traditional observers assume that parameters are fixed and known [Dochain \(2003\)](#), adaptive observers integrate an online parameter adaptation law into their dynamics [Kreisselmeier \(1974\)](#). Although there are proposals in the literature for extended versions of the Luenberger or Kalman observer aimed at jointly estimating states and parameters [Afri et al. \(2016\)](#); [Deng et al. \(2013\)](#), these proposals often lack certain desired features, such as the ability to explicitly track unknown parameters [Zhang \(2002\)](#). This limitation makes the adaptive observer design more suitable for digital twins. Integrating mechanistic computational models with adaptive observer algorithms would enable the transition from *static* computational systems to digital twins.

In this work, we present a framework for calibrating digital twins via adaptive observers. The next section focuses on classical observers and their limitations. Then, the concept of an adaptive observer, along with the adaptive digital twin framework, is presented. Next, we discuss the applicability of digital twins to viral infections, drug-resistant pathogens, and co-infections. We end with conclusions and relevant insights.

Classical Observers

Reconstructing unmeasured states from partial measurable outputs of a system is a central problem in control theory [Simon \(2006\)](#). Classical observers, like the Luenberger observer for deterministic systems and the Kalman filter for stochastic ones, offer good performance. In the Luenberger observer case, the design process ensures asymptotic convergence of the estimated states to their true values. In the Kalman filter case, the design is based on a probabilistic estimator that minimizes the mean square estimation error by incorporating both the process and measurement noise statistics [Kalman et al. \(1960\)](#).

While the Kalman filter was initially developed for linear systems, the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) or Extended Kalman Observer (EKO) extends these concepts to non-linear systems by linearizing the state dynamics at each time step [Simon \(2006\)](#). In general, the Luenberger observer has a simple implementation and low computational cost, whereas the Kalman filter is more computationally demanding, but offers good performance under noise and uncertainty. The above-mentioned observers typically assume full knowledge of system parameters. When this assumption is not satisfied, their performance can degrade significantly [Dochain \(2003\)](#).

Adaptive Observers

The idea of combining state observation with parameter adaptation dates back to early works, such as [Luders and Narendra \(1973\)](#) and [Kreisselmeier \(1974\)](#), where convergence under restrictive conditions was es-

Table 1. Key aspects of comparison between Luenberger, Kalman, and Adaptive observers.

Aspect	Luenberger Observer	Kalman Filter	Adaptive Observer
System class	Deterministic	Stochastic	LTV, MIMO, and state-affine
Estimation objective	States only	States (optimal in mean-square sense)	States + parameters
Design requirement	Observability of (A, C)	Uniform complete observability	Stabilizability of (A, C) + persistent excitation
Convergence guarantee	Asymptotic (if detectable)	Under strong observability + noise assumptions	Global exponential (noise free); bounded mean under noise
Robustness	weak to parametric mismatch	Robust to Gaussian noise	Robust to bounded disturbances and parameter drift
Computational complexity	Low (static gain)	Moderate/high (covariance)	Moderate/high (observer + adaptation law)
Applications	Classical control	Tracking, navigation	Adaptive control, fault detection, digital twins

Table 2. Summary of joint state-parameter approaches.

No.	Observer technique	Reference
1	Luenberger-based observers	Afri et al. (2015, 2016)
2	Kalman-based observers	Deng et al. (2013) ; Van Der Merwe and Wan (2001) ; Evensen (2009) ; Afshari et al. (2017)
3	Observer-based estimators	Dochain (2003) ; Ali et al. (2015) ; Perrier et al. (2000)
4	Adaptive observers	Besancon et al. (2006) ; Zhang (2002) ; Rodríguez et al. (2015)

established. Later, in [Bastin and Gevers \(1988\)](#), a systematic design approach for single-output nonlinear systems was introduced, employing canonical transformations to simplify the parameter dependence. With these foundational results, later on, works such as [Besancon et al. \(2006\)](#) and [Zhang \(2002\)](#) extended the framework to MIMO time-varying systems and state-affine nonlinear systems, overcoming many of the structural limitations of the earlier approaches. Formally, adaptive observers consider state-affine systems of the form:

$$\dot{x}(t) = A(t)x(t) + B(t)u(t) + \Psi(t)\theta \quad (1a)$$

$$y(t) = C(t)x(t), \quad (1b)$$

where $x(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$, $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$, and $y(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the states, inputs, and outputs of the system, respectively; matrices $A(t)$, $B(t)$, and $C(t)$ are known time varying matrices; $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the unknown vector of parameters that is assumed constant; and $\Psi(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times p}$ is a matrix of known signals. Unlike the discussed traditional observers, the adaptive observer design takes advantage of the state-affine form with respect to θ and constructs a coupled scheme. This results in a stabilizing state observer, coupled with a parameter adaptation law [Zhang \(2002\)](#). The convergence of adaptive observers rests on two key assumptions: (i) the existence of a stabilizing observer gain $K(t)$ for the nominal system and (ii) persistent excitation (PE) of the regressor signals, which ensures identifiability of the parameters. Under these conditions, adaptive observers achieve global exponential convergence in noise-free settings and robustness in the presence of bounded disturbances.

Adaptive observers differentiate them from the classical observers (see [Table 1](#)). First, it is more suitable for both state and parameter estimation. Second, it has achievable design requirements. Third, it has global and exponential convergence when noise is not considered and bounded mean when noise is considered. Fourth, it is robust against bounded disturbances and parameters. Lastly, it has a moderate-to-high computational complexity, depending on the problem dimension, i.e.,

the considered number of states-parameters to be estimated. [Table 1](#) summarizes the main applications for each type of observers.

Although the adaptive observer was originally developed for joint state-parameter estimation, it is not the sole proposal available in the literature for addressing this task. For instance, in [Afri et al. \(2016\)](#), the authors present the theoretical formulation of a nonlinear Luenberger observer approach for state and parameter estimation. This proposal offers a simpler, globally stable alternative to the adaptive observers; however, in this case, parameter estimates are not directly produced, limiting its role to cases in which tracking parameters is not the primary task. In [Deng et al. \(2013\)](#); [Van Der Merwe and Wan \(2001\)](#), extended formulations of the Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) can be found for joint state-parameter estimation; in these approaches, the augmented state method is implemented.

The aforementioned approaches come with high computational costs, and, moreover, the augmented state methodology increases system dimension and leads to tuning issues that could result in biased parameter estimates or even filter divergence. For a comprehensive discussion on Gaussian filters used in state and parameter estimation, readers may refer to [Afshari et al. \(2017\)](#). Joint state-parameter estimation algorithms are summarized in [Table 2](#).

Figure 2. Adaptive digital twin framework. The dynamical update of the virtual representation is performed through an adaptive observer algorithm that perform, in a continuous manner, the estimation of unmeasurable states (virtual sensors, state observer block) and the model parameter recalibration (dynamical model update from physical twin data, parameter updating block).

The adaptive observer, while successfully applied in real settings [Rodríguez et al. \(2015\)](#), has two notable drawbacks: (i) its computational demand—this method necessitates the calculation of matrix inverses, and the computational cost escalates as the problem dimension increases; and (ii) its reliance on a continuous form formulation—this limitation becomes evident when implementing this strategy in situations where sparse sensor measurements are prevalent. These challenges highlight the need for alternative approaches that can maintain efficiency and effectiveness in environments with limited data. Exploring new methods that reduce computational complexity or adapt to discrete measurement scenarios could enhance the applicability of observer designs in diverse real-world contexts.

Figure 2 describes our proposal of adaptive observers for digital twins, i.e., the adaptive digital twin framework. In this case, adaptive observer algorithms are used for dynamical updating of model parameters (see the parameter-updating block) at the same pace that new data becomes available and, more importantly, without triggering complete retraining cycles of complex optimization methods for parameter identification—*Static vs Continuous*. This approach has the potential to enable better monitoring of key biological markers, as well as enhance predictions for virtual drug and therapy testing. This would enable a new paradigm in precision medicine for patients with infectious diseases.

Developing Immune Digital Twins

The immune system plays a critical role in the development and progression of numerous significant diseases

[Niarakis et al. \(2024\)](#). Consequently, the development of a reliable software representation of the immune system, known as an Immune Digital Twin (IDT), could significantly impact healthcare and biological research [Laubenbacher et al. \(2022\)](#). As expected, there is a large interdisciplinary and international research community focused on developing an IDT [Wang et al. \(2024\)](#); [National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine \(2023\)](#); [Vodovotz \(2023\)](#). However, the immune system response is complex and varies among diseases and patients [Paul \(2012\)](#), which presents significant technical challenges that require careful consideration.

Accordingly, the integration of adaptive observers into an IDT represents a paradigm shift from *static* to *adaptive* computational models that will help practitioners towards therapy selection, optimal decision making for specific patients, and allow disease prediction.

Currently, there are promising applications of MDTs, such as the living heart project [Levine et al. \(2022\)](#); [Corral-Acero et al. \(2020\)](#) or the artificial pancreas project [Breton et al. \(2020\)](#); [Man et al. \(2014\)](#). This adaptive digital twin framework is expected to broaden these promising applications by enabling systems capable of continuously updating and iteratively reparameterizing, closing the gap between static models and true digital twins. The following subsections demonstrate how adaptive observers can revolutionize personalized medicine across different infectious disease contexts.

A. Viral Infections

Viral infections pose unique challenges for IDT implementation due to their rapid dynamics and complex interactions with the host immune response. Mathemati-

cal models of viral infections have been instrumental in understanding disease progression, but often lack the adaptability required for personalized treatment strategies [Suen et al. \(2017\)](#); [Wu et al. \(2011\)](#); [Miao et al. \(2011\)](#). The use of adaptive observers can enable the continuous monitoring of the immune system response by using viral load measures, while also tracking parameter drifts according to the parameter adaptation law.

For HIV infection, where long-term management and treatment strategies are critical, adaptive observers can predict CD4+ T cell counts, viral reservoir dynamics, and drug resistance evolution [Hernandez-Vargas \(2017\)](#).

This tracking procedure can be performed by the adaptive observer using patient-specific data pertinent to the HIV infection, such as viral load data and CD4+ T cell counts. In the same way, adaptive observers require a dynamical mechanistic model of the HIV infection, in which case it would be possible to estimate and monitor changes in key parameters, such as infection or proliferation rates of infected cells and reservoirs [Hernandez-Vargas and Middleton \(2013\)](#). These capabilities play an important role for aging HIV patients, where immunological heterogeneity and treatment complications require personalized therapeutic approaches [Hernandez-Vargas et al. \(2013\)](#).

In influenza infections, adaptive observers can monitor the three stages of the infection process, which are initial viral replication, immune response activation, and either resolution of infection or further complications thereof [Boianelli et al. \(2015\)](#); [Hernandez-Vargas and Meyer-Hermann \(2012\)](#). In a similar manner, the adaptive framework, coupled with a relevant influenza model and the pathogen load measurements, enables prediction of disease progression, thus allowing for optimal timing of antiviral interventions, which are particularly crucial in elderly patients where immune responses are often impaired [Hernandez-Vargas et al. \(2014\)](#). Moreover, recent applications have demonstrated the utility of mathematical models in predicting influenza-specific CD8+ T cell responses and optimizing treatment strategies [Jhutti et al. \(2022\)](#); [Parra-Rojas et al. \(2018\)](#). Thus, enabling the monitoring of inflammatory responses with adaptive observers could improve diagnosis and prognosis.

B. Tracking Evolution of Antibiotic Resistance

The emergence of drug-resistant pathogens represents one of the most pressing challenges in modern medicine, with traditional static models inadequately capturing the dynamic evolution of resistance mechanisms [Levy and Marshall \(2004\)](#); [Murray et al. \(2022\)](#). Adaptive observers offer a transformative approach by enabling continuous tracking of pathogen evolution and real-time adjustment of therapeutic strategies.

In the context of antibiotic resistance, adaptive observers can monitor bacterial population dynamics, resistance gene expression, and the emergence of resistant subpopulations during treatment. This capability is essential for implementing collateral sensitivity-based cycling ther-

apies, where the order and timing of antibiotic administration must be carefully optimized to prevent resistance development [Tetteh et al. \(2023\)](#); [Imamovic and Sommer \(2013\)](#).

Mathematical models incorporating control theory approaches have shown promise in developing cutting-edge methods to personalize treatment strategies and mitigate drug resistance evolution [Hernandez-Vargas et al. \(2011\)](#). In this scenario, by iteratively updating model parameters based on patient-specific measurements, adaptive observers can predict when current therapeutic approaches may fail and recommend alternative treatment strategies before clinical deterioration occurs [Anderson et al. \(2025\)](#). This proactive approach represents a significant advancement over reactive treatment modifications based on observed therapeutic failure. Modeling heterogeneous bacterial populations and predicting the evolution of resistance under different selective pressures provides clinicians with unprecedented insight into treatment optimization [Alavez-Ramírez et al. \(2007\)](#); [Bhagunde et al. \(2015\)](#).

C. Co-Infections

Co-infections, particularly viral-bacterial combinations such as influenza and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, represent some of the most complex scenarios for IDT implementation. The synergistic interactions between pathogens, combined with host immune system modulation, create highly dynamic systems that require sophisticated adaptive control strategies [McCullers \(2014\)](#); [Ballinger and Standiford \(2010\)](#).

Alveolar macrophages serve as critical sentinels in respiratory co-infections, with their functional states determining infection outcomes through complex polarization mechanisms between M1 (inflammatory) and M2 (healing) phenotypes [Gordon and Martinez \(2010\)](#); [Mills and Ley \(2014\)](#). Adaptive observers can track these macrophage dynamics, monitoring key cytokine profiles, such as IFN- γ and IL-6, that determine susceptibility to secondary bacterial infections [Duvigneau et al. \(2016\)](#); [Sharma-Chawla et al. \(2019\)](#). This capability of the adaptive framework addresses a major knowledge gap in co-infection modeling, where static representations fail to capture the spatial and temporal modulation of immune cell functions. The adaptive framework enables integration of multi-scale data, from cellular immune responses to tissue-level pathogen dynamics. For influenza-*pneumococcal* co-infections, adaptive observers can track the transition from viral-mediated immune suppression to bacterial invasion and systemic dissemination [Almocera et al. \(2019\)](#); [Boianelli et al. \(2015\)](#). This multi-pathogen adaptive modeling approach provides insights into the timing-dependent effects of therapeutic interventions, enabling optimization of both antiviral and antibiotic therapies.

Through these applications, adaptive observers can play

a crucial role in the development of immune digital twins, leveraging the transition from *static* computational tools into *adaptive*, patient-specific platforms that hold the potential of continuous learning and adaptation. This evolution is essential for addressing the complexity and variability inherent in infectious disease management, ultimately improving patient outcomes through personalized therapeutic strategies.

Conclusion

Medical Digital Twins hold enormous promise for personalized medicine, but their current reliance on static mechanistic models limits their effectiveness. Digital twins must continuously evolve, assimilating patient-specific data in real time to remain faithful to the biological system they represent. In this work, we propose that adaptive observers provide a natural and powerful framework to achieve this transformation. Unlike classical observers, such as the Luenberger or Kalman filter, adaptive observers jointly estimate unmeasured states and unknown parameters, enabling continuous recalibration of the computational model.

By bridging control theory with biomedical applications, adaptive observers open the door to Medical Digital Twins that are no longer static approximations but are instead dynamic, living systems. Such twins could adapt to disease progression, account for inter- and inpatient variability, and anticipate treatment resistance. The cases of viral infections, drug-resistant pathogens, and co-infections illustrate the urgency of this capability, where evolving dynamics demand equally adaptive models.

Looking ahead, integrating adaptive observers into MDTs represents more than a technical improvement: it is a paradigm shift. It moves digital twins from being descriptive tools to prescriptive, evolving companions in clinical decision-making. The potential reward is transformative: adaptive observer-driven digital twins could become the cornerstone of a new era in precision medicine.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Author Contributions

Juan E. Sereno: Writing – review, editing, Visualization, and Investigation. Havilah Neujahr: Writing – review and editing. Esteban A. Hernandez-Vargas: Writing – review, funding, supervision and editing.

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